

**STUDY OF VARIOUS BASALT AND READY-MADE PRODUCTS THAT
CAN BE OBTAINED FROM BASALT IN THE DIFFERENT
CONTINENTS OF THE WORLD.**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10279484>

About 70% of the Earth's surface is made up of basalts, which are igneous rocks formed when magma on the surface cools and solidifies. Rock-melting products are highly marketable and can be thought of as the forerunners of glass-ceramic technology. These materials are guaranteed since they can be used to convert inexpensive natural raw materials into goods with superior thermal, chemical, and mechanical qualities. In this thesis, the composition of basalt in several regions is analyzed. Meanwhile, the data about various types of ready-made products which can be obtained from basalt is given.

The characteristics of basaltic rocks include a high degree of hardness, a dark color, fine grain, and a silica content ranging from 45 to 52% by mass. Its magma has a low viscosity because of the low silica content. Pyroxene, olivine, plagioclase, and other common basalt minerals [1].

Alkaline basaltic and sub-alkaline basaltic are the two main categories of basaltic rocks. These belong to the subgroups of calcium-alkaline basalts and tholeiitic basalts. A type of chemical element known as silicates, which are created by structures comprising cations and anions, make up the great bulk of igneous rocks [2-4]. Typically, the oxide content in rocks is stated as a weight percentage. The chemical compositions of basalts from various parts of the earth are compared in Table 1 to assess the likelihood of producing glass ceramics.

Table 1 - Chemical composition (wt.%) of basalts from different regions of the world

Oxide (wt. %)	Thrace region, Turkey	Southern Anatolia, Turkey	Arkhangelsk, Russia	SGF, Brasil	Vrelo-Kopaonik, Serbia	Vrelo-Kopaonik, Serbia	Egyptian basalt, Egypt	Osmonsoy basalt, Uzbekistan
SiO ₂	45.91	43.18	45.83	51.42	56.21	49.33	48.39	45.7
Al ₂ O ₃	12.16	13.15	15.34	13.81	18.61	16.13	13.98	20.83
Fe ₂ O ₃	10.74 ^a	13.49 ^a	1.52	7.36	1.15	3.81	12.63 ^a	8.30 ^a
FeO	-	-	9.16	5.83	2.97	2.68	-	-
CaO	9.12	9.67	7.72	10.45	7.78	8.87	9.16	8.92
MgO	12.16	8.48	6.78	6.29	3.40	6.48	6.92	4.95
K ₂ O	4.25 ^b	2.78	1.33	0.70	3.37	2.70	0.79	0.42

Na ₂ O	-	4.27	3.37	2.45	4.73	3.30	2.50	3.39
TiO ₂	2.93	3.34	7.61	1.37	1.11	1.94	-	0.79
MnO	-	-	0.21	0.20	-	0.14	-	-
Mn ₂ O ₃	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.1743
P ₂ O ₅	-	0.96	-	0.14	-	-	-	0.06
H ₂ O	-	-	-	-	-	1.57	-	-
Cr ₂ O ₃	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.047
ППВ ^c	2.72	-	-	-	-	-	5.32	3.35
a FeO+Fe₂O₃ b K₂O+Na₂O c Потеря при прокаливании								

Iron may be shown to exist in two oxidation states in basalt composition: Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺, which combine to create iron oxide II (FeO) and iron oxide III (Fe₂O₃), respectively. The chemical makeup and circumstances of the basaltic rock formation will determine the Fe³⁺/Fe²⁺ ratio. According to Holand and Beall [5], the production of glass ceramics is largely dependent on iron in its two oxidation states. According to the scientists, if the original rock composition's Fe₂O₃/FeO ratio is more than 0.5, heat-treated basalt glasses may create glass-ceramic materials.

Since it is an extrusive igneous rock, the TAS diagram, which connects the mass amount (%m.) of SiO₂ as a function of alkaline content (sum of mass percentages of Na₂O and K₂O), may be used to identify its mineralogical composition. Igneous rocks can be categorized as ultrabasic (SiO₂ < 45%), basic (52% < SiO₂ < 45%), intermediate (66% < SiO₂ < 52%), or acidic (SiO₂ > 66%) based on the quantity of silica they contain.

In its natural state, basalt is used as a raw material for walls, pavements, and sidewalks as well as for cladding panels because of its strong resistance to wear and chemicals. Also, basalt is widely utilized as an inexpensive raw material to make gravel, which is the primary aggregate used in civil construction. Gran gravel is a broken piece of rock that is sorted for usage based on its grain size after being crushed and then selected. Every kind of gravel has a distinct use in civil engineering, including the creation of concrete, pavement, buildings, railroads, tunnels, and even dams [6, 7].

Different research indicated that because of the dielectric characteristics of basaltic glass-ceramic materials, they might be used as semiconductors and insulators. As per the findings, low dielectric materials in the electronics covering sector may be derived from basalt glass-ceramic [8].

A few studies have shown that basalt glass-ceramics-covered steel might be used to increase these materials' resistance to heat, wear, corrosion,

oxidation, and erosion. The metal is coated with basalt powder using a plasma spraying technique, and crystallization is then achieved by heat treatment. The research produced positive and encouraging findings (see, for example, [9,10] and the references therein).

Due to its intriguing qualities, basaltic rocks have also sparked a lot of attention in technology for their potential application in the manufacturing of fiber. These are inorganic fibers that are inexpensive, natural, and ecological and have good mechanical strength, resilience to high temperatures, outstanding chemical stability, and ease of processing. They are also non-toxic. Typically, theirs is on par with or higher than fiberglass. The following fibers have different elasticity moduli (GPa): basalt fiber, 95–115; aramid fiber (1414), 124–130; E glass fiber, 73–78; S glass fiber, 83; and carbon fiber (T300), 230–240 [11-13].

The basaltic rock is melted at 1400 °C to produce fiber. To create continuous basalt fibers, the melt is extruded through a platinum-rhodium mold under hydrostatic pressure. Depending on the application, cutting machines are used to cut the fibers to the appropriate length. The fiber's measurements fall between 10 and 20 μ m for diameter and 3 and 130 mm for length. The fact that basalt fibers are less expensive to create and need less energy than carbon and glass fibers is one of their main advantages [14].

Basalt fibers are primarily used in the creation of composite materials. In civil engineering, fibers are mostly utilized to strengthen concrete. Additionally, basalt fibers are utilized in the production of superior, lighter hybrid composite materials (i.e., materials that include many fiber types within a single matrix) for use in infrastructure applications. The oxidation and crystallization of basalt fibers at temperatures beyond about 300 °C pose a constraint on their application in structural polymer matrix composites. The fiber's tensile strength is reduced as a result of these surface and microstructural alterations, rendering it more delicate [15,16].

According to the results of the research, it is possible to synthesize several ready-made products from basalt, including colored glasses, glass fibers, composite materials, etc. Of course, it is advisable to use additional raw materials together with basalt to synthesize such products

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